

Declaration Form Use of GenAI in an Assignment

This form must be completed by the student who undertakes to declare their use of the GenAI.

Course code:	Click or tap here to enter text.
Semester & year:	Click or tap here to enter text.
Teacher's name:	Click or tap here to enter text.

Level of use authorized by the teacher

LEVEL 0	LEVEL 1	LEVEL 2	LEVEL 3	LEVEL 4
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Prohibited Use	Limited use	Targeted use	Framed use	Free use

For the purpose of:

- Learning
- Language

Students' name:	Click or tap here to enter text.
Production title:	Click or tap here to enter text.

Unless otherwise noted, the content of this work is available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). You are encouraged to share and adapt it, according to the following condition, which is to attribute parenthood to the work.

Translated by Bowles, E. & Beaudet, M. (2024) from the original document by Cabana, M. (2024). [Formulaire de déclaration : utilisation de l'IA dans une production étudiante](#). Service de soutien à la formation, Université de Sherbrooke. Sous licence [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

The illustrations used in this document are inspired by vector images from the [Flaticon](https://www.flaticon.com/) website, created by Yogi Aprellyanto, as well as Freepik. They have been personalized by the author of this document.

Declared uses

	Uses	Y	N	GenAI used	Queries used ¹
LEVEL 1	Learning:				
	Get inspired	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Generate ideas	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Explore a topic to better understand it	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Generate material to learn	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Other use: Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Language:				
	Identify your mistakes and have them explained to you	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Rephrase a text	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Generate an outline to help structure a text	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Translate a text	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Other use: Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>			
LEVEL 2	Analyze content	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Get feedback	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Evaluate the quality of your work based on criteria	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Ask to be confronted with your ideas, your approach	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

	Uses	Y	N	GenAI used	Queries used ¹
	Use problem-solving processes	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Other use: Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
LEVEL 3	Summarize or write parts of a text	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Create and adapt a text or an example of the product	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Perform mathematical calculations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Write computer code	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Solve complex problems	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Answer a question	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Create images or other multimedia content	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Other use: Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
LEVEL 4	Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
	Click or tap here to enter text.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

¹ The answers provided by generative artificial intelligence must be placed in the appendix of the final assignment.

Additional information (if applicable):

Click or tap here to enter text.